

Ultra-Thin Absorber based on Phase Change Metamaterial Superlattice

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Abstract— In this paper, a superlattice VO_2/SiO_2 metamaterial on a lossy substrate is designed to create a near perfect absorber with tunability across the infrared spectrum. We selected VO_2 as it presents a dielectric to metal-like phase change slightly above room temperature. Additionally, the slightly lossy nature of high-temperature VO_2 presents comparable and small components (real and imaginary) of the complex refractive index across portions of the visible and infrared. Coupled with a limited conductivity substrate, VO_2 has been employed to create highly absorbing/emitting structures where the thickness of the VO_2 is ultra-thin ($t \ll \lambda/4n$). Nevertheless, metal-like VO_2 does not possess comparable and small components of the complex refractive index across the entire infrared spectrum, which limits the universality of this ultra-thin VO_2 absorber design. Here we employ an ultra-thin superlattice of VO_2/SiO_2 to create a composite metamaterial that is readily designed for high absorbance across the infrared spectrum.

Keywords—metamaterial, vanadium dioxide, absorber, emitter, superlattice, infrared

I. INTRODUCTION

A dielectric to metal-like phase change occurs for VO_2 at temperatures slightly above room temperature. This has sparked interest in VO_2 as a coating on windows of commercial buildings to reflect sunlight on warm days. Unfortunately, this high-temperature reflective state is inherently non-emitting, which is counter to applications such as radiators that need to eject heat at elevated temperatures. This phase change can be generated actively via an applied electric field or a local heating as well as passively via a temperature change of the entire structure or system.

The use of slightly lossy material was recently proposed to create a single high absorbance layer that is much thinner than the traditional quarter wavelength design. [1] The key insight was to use a material with optical properties intermediate between a (lossless) dielectric and a (perfect electric conductor) metal on a partially lossy substrate. [2] Many semiconductors particularly metal oxides present this intermediate complex dielectric state across large portions of the infrared. The material VO_2 is particularly interesting as it undergoes a phase transition near 50°C . The material is a dielectric below the critical point and is metal-like above the transition point. This is of interest for a variety of applications including switchable antenna structures.

II. DESIGN

Previous work on dielectrics with strong optical absorption deposited on metal-like materials with limited conductivity has leveraged the non-trivial reflection phase shift at the interfaces. [2] Specifically, the reflection phase shift is intermediate to 0 and π , when one of the materials has a complex refractive index, $n_c = n + ik$, with comparable n and k . Therefore, the structure can accumulate a near-zero reflectance via multiple optical phase shifts at the interfaces. This is in contrast to the gradual phase change over the optical thickness as in traditional wavelength-scale film optics such as a quarter wavelength mirror.

The criteria to achieve near unity absorbance are a specific interplay of the VO_2 thickness, wavelength-dependent VO_2 refractive index, and the wavelength-dependent substrate refractive index. Fig 1. displays the absorbance of a VO_2 layer as a function of thickness on a sapphire substrate. A high absorbance state is possible for a thickness of 37nm , which is remarkable as this corresponds to an optical thickness of $\lambda/53n$.

Fig. 1. Absorbance of a VO_2 thin film as a function of thickness on a sapphire substrate at a wavelength of $11.75 \mu\text{m}$. The peak absorbance occurs for a VO_2 film on 37nm .

Although the absorbance is high with a 37nm film, examination of Fig. 2 shows that a significant fraction (approximately 10%) of the infrared light is reflected from this structure. For this particular complex dielectric constant of the VO_2 and the sapphire substrate at a wavelength of $11.75 \mu\text{m}$,

there is not a thickness that allows the reflection coefficients to return to zero.

Fig. 2 (top) Reflectivity, (middle) reflection coefficient, and (bottom) phase angle of a VO₂ thin film as a function of thickness on a sapphire substrate at a wavelength of 11.75 μm.

Inspection of Fig. 3 reveals that a perfect absorbing refractive index condition theoretically exists for a 37nm film on sapphire at a wavelength of 11.75 μm. Unfortunately, this complex refractive index does not match the experimental VO₂ refractive index at this wavelength. A summary of Figs 1-3, is that a high absorbance state is available for an ultra-thin VO₂ layer on sapphire at this wavelength, but a perfect absorber/emitter is not available at any thickness.

Fig. 3. Theoretical absorbance of a 37nm VO₂ layer on sapphire at a wavelength of 11.75 μm as a function of real (n) and imaginary (k) complex refractive index coefficient. A near unity absorbance condition exists for a hypothetical film with a refractive index n = 8, and k = 4. For reference, the experimental refractive index of VO₂ and SiO₂ are also displayed.

A solution to this non-unity absorber limitation, is to form a superlattice with another layer. Fig. 4 show that 2nm VO₂ / 8

nm SiO₂ superlattice displays an absorbance of approximately 92%. As each individual VO₂ and SiO₂ layer thickness is much less than the infrared wavelength, it is safe to describe the superlattice as a composite layer.

Fig. 4. Absorbance of a 20x VO₂/SiO₂ superlattice as a function of VO₂ and SiO₂ layer thickness.

Fig. 5. Effective parallel and perpendicular permittivity of the VO₂/SiO₂ superlattice as a function of fill fraction. The parallel and perpendicular terms are relative to the surface of the superlattice.

Viewing the superlattice as a single composite layer provides greater insight into the behavior of the material. In the superlattice the effective perpendicular permittivity can be expressed by

$$\epsilon_{\perp} = \frac{\epsilon_{Metal} \epsilon_{Dielectric}}{f \epsilon_{Metal} + (1-f) \epsilon_{Dielectric}} = \frac{1}{\frac{d_{Metal}}{\epsilon_{Metal}} + \frac{d_{Dielectric}}{\epsilon_{Dielectric}}}, \quad (1)$$

where f is the fill fraction of the metallic VO₂. Additionally, in the superlattice the parallel permittivity can be expressed by

$$\epsilon_{\parallel} = f \epsilon_{Metal} + (1-f) \epsilon_{Dielectric} = \frac{d_{Metal} \epsilon_{Metal} + d_{Dielectric} \epsilon_{Dielectric}}{d_{Metal} + d_{Dielectric}}, \quad (2)$$

where the metal term refers to the metallic VO_2 and the dielectric term refers to the SiO_2 .

Fig. 6. Absorbance of a VO_2 - SiO_2 composite layer as a function of thickness on a sapphire substrate. The calculation is based on an effective parallel complex refractive index of $2.8295 + 2.4399i$ interacting with an on-axis incident wave.

The absorbance of this composite stack as a function of thickness on a sapphire substrate is observable in Fig. 6. The peak absorbance of 97% for a thickness of 190nm is remarkable in that the total optical thickness is $\lambda/22n$. Creating a sub-wavelength superlattice metamaterial allow the effective creation of new optical properties that allow near unity absorption.

III. CONCLUSION

The paper present a simple technique to ease the application and increase effectiveness of ultra-thin lossy layers as the basis for near-unity absorber/emitter structures. Additionally, the phase change nature of VO_2 is useful for systems and devices that require a passive or active change in emittance.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. A. Kats, D. Sharma, J. Lin, P. Genevet, R. Blanchard, Z. Yang, M. M. Qazilbash, D. N. Basov, S. Ramanathan, F. Capasso, "Ultra-thin perfect absorber employing a tunable phase change material," *Appl. Phys. Letts*, vol. 101, pp. 221101, 2012.
- [2] M. A. Kats, F. Capasso, "Ultra-thin optical interference coatings on rough and flexible substrates," *Appl. Phys. Letts*, vol. 105, pp. 131108, 2014.